

A Review of Ed-Tech Sector in India

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ABSTRACT

This qualitative research paper aims to provide a comprehensive review of the Ed-Tech sector in India by examining its current state, identifying key trends, and exploring the factors contributing to its growth and challenges. It investigates the diverse range of educational technologies being employed, including online platforms, mobile applications, virtual classrooms, and adaptive learning systems. The research critically examines the effectiveness and impact of these technologies on teaching and learning outcomes, as well as their influence on student engagement, accessibility, and equity. This research delves into the factors driving the growth of the Ed-Tech sector in India, such as increasing smartphone penetration, improved internet connectivity, favorable government initiatives, and changing attitudes toward online learning. It also investigates the challenges faced by the sector, such as the digital divide, inadequate teacher training, concerns regarding data privacy and security, and the need for regulatory frameworks. It examines their strategies, business models, and partnerships, highlighting successful practices and lessons learned. By providing an in-depth analysis of the Ed-Tech sector in India, this research paper offers valuable insights for policymakers, educators, investors, and stakeholders in the field of education. The outcomes of the study entail to the previous literature vis Ed-Tech, helping to inform future initiatives, policies, and investments in the Indian education system

INTRODUCTION

What is Ed-Tech?

The term "Education Technology" can also be abbreviated as "Ed-Tech." Utilizing computers, computer programs, and educational systems, offers students, employees, and other users the opportunity to further their knowledge and receive training (Singh, Vidani, & Nagoria, 2016).

The far reaching field of schooling innovation envelops not just the equipment and programming utilized in what is usually known as "remote learning," "distance learning," or "online training," yet additionally the speculations of learning and extending examination into the best ways of granting new information and abilities to individuals (Singh, Vidani, & Nagoria, 2016).

CFI, which was one of the earliest companies in the Ed-Tech industry, provides existing and prospective professionals in the field of global financial services with training as well as certification (Singh, Vidani, & Nagoria, 2016).

Summary

- Due to the multiple benefits it gives to both teachers and students, online learning is continuing to grow and is being utilized more and more frequently (Mala, Vidani, & Solanki, 2016).
- Ed-Tech, which stands for educational technology, refers to the entire field of computer-assisted education and training (Dhere, Vidani, & Solanki, 2016).
- CFI was one of the first organizations to offer financial professionals online education, certification, and training... (Dhere, Vidani, & Solanki, 2016)

The Growth of Ed-Tech

The history of educational technology goes back much farther than most people realize. The use of computers in the educational process is a natural outgrowth of scientific and technological advancement (Singh & Vidani, 2016). Around the center of the 20th century, schools and preparation offices began utilizing effectively accessible innovation, for example, copiers and media learning through preparing recordings (Vidani & Plaha, 2016).

The use of computers to aid in the teaching of subjects like mathematics and spelling was first tried in classrooms in the 1960s. By 2010, it was expected that about six million students in the United States alone will be enrolled in online courses (Solanki & Vidani, 2016). The proliferation of online education followed the advent of widespread internet access (Vidani, 2016).

The Open University in the UK and the University of British Columbia in Canada were among the earliest innovators in interactive online education (Biharani & Vidani, 2018). This facilitated conversation and instruction between professors and students, as well as among students themselves (Vidani, 2018).

Due to advancements in areas such as video (Vidani, Chack, & Rathod, 2017), conferencing software and multimedia resources, Ed-Tech is now more accessible and effective than ever before (Odedra, Rabadiya, & Vidani, 2018). A

few examples of recent developments in the field of education technology include the usage of "robots" in the classroom to help students take notes and the implementation of blockchain technologies to help professors grade student work (Sachaniya, Vora, & Vidani, 2019).

Advantages Offered by Ed-Tech

There are many significant advantages to using technology in the classroom. Teachers believe that there is a wide range of how and how quickly pupils learn (Vidani, 2019).

Some pupils, for instance, learn best via reading, while others do better with visually presented materials. Thanks to Ed-Tech, students can get their education from wherever they feel will be most beneficial to them (Vidani, Jacob, & Patel, 2019).

Students who want to take their courses online often highlight the flexibility it provides in terms of when and where they can get their education (Odedra, Rabadiya, & Vidani, 2018). The ability to access online learning whenever convenient for the learner makes education and continuous professional training far more available to a wide range of people in a wide range of contexts (Vidani & Singh, 2017).

Those who already have full-time jobs and would have a hard time fitting in traditional university lectures may benefit greatly from this option (Pathak & Vidani, 2016).

As one of the most obvious benefits of Ed-Tech, the possibility of huge financial savings in the classroom is an attractive one (Vidani J. N., 2022). It is possible to get a high-quality education online for far less money than it would cost to enroll at a university or even a local community college (Vidani & Plaha, 2017).

Online schooling makes getting a degree or other expert certificate undeniably more open to anyone with any interest in doing as such at a more reasonable Expense (Vidani & Dholakia, 2020).

Benefits of Ed-Tech for Students

Students of all ages are benefiting from the increased learning opportunities provided by technology, which also promotes diversity and collaboration in the classroom. The following are five key ways that educational technology is already altering the way that children learn (Vidani, Meghrajani, & Siddarth, 2023).

Increased Collaboration

Tablets and cloud-based software are enabling students to work together more effectively in the homeroom. Tablets stocked with educational games and online classes equip kids with the tools they need to work together on issues (Rathod, Meghrajani, & Vidani, 2022). Cloud-based apps, on the other hand, let students upload their work and have virtual discussions about their ideas and get help from classmates without ever meeting in person (Vidani & Das, 2021).

24/7 Access to Learning

IoT gadgets are making it simpler for understudies to take part completely in web-based study halls (Vidani J. N., 2022). Students can now do their schoolwork whenever and wherever they have access to Wi-Fi and the cloud through a connected device, not only while physically present in a classroom. This includes the school bus and at home (Vidani J. N., 2022).

There are various applications that assist understudies and educators with keeping in contact in the event of inquiries or on the other hand assuming an understudy needs to make an instructor aware of a crisis (Saxena & Vidani, 2023).

“Flipping” the Classroom

Ed-Tech is revolutionizing the way we think about teaching and learning in the classroom (Vidani, 2015). In most cases, students first attend class to learn new material or listen to lectures, then go home to complete homework and other projects (Vidani & Solanki, 2015). Students can now hear lectures at home at their own leisure via learning applications and video lectures, freeing up class time for students to work on group projects together (Saxena & Vidani, 2023). Kids thrive in this style of classroom because they are challenged to think critically, express their individuality, and cooperate with their peers (Vidani, 2015).

Personalized Educational Experiences

With the use of Ed-Tech tools, educators may tailor their lessons to the needs of each of their pupils (Saxena & Vidani, 2023). The goal of this approach is to personalize the learning process for each student (Solanki & Vidani, 2016).

Video content technologies allow students to grow at their natural speed and check their understanding of the topic by pausing and rewinding lectures (Vidani, 2016). In order to help students who are having difficulty, teachers can use data analytics to determine which students are having problems and which lessons they are having trouble with (Bhatt, Patel, & Vidani, 2017).

Rather than using anxiety-inducing tests to evaluate student progress, educators are increasingly turning to apps that can provide a more accurate picture of students' underlying abilities (Pradhan, Tshogay, & Vidani, 2016). Utilizing persistent measurements that uncover learning designs, instructors can configure individualized illustration plans in light of every understudy's novel arrangement of qualities and shortcomings (Mala, Vidani, & Solanki, 2016).

Attention-Grabbing Lessons

Do you recall ever daydreaming or only half-listening in a class? With so many distractions in the classroom, including students' own electronic devices and the wider world, it's more important than ever to design lessons that are both interesting and useful (Dhere, Vidani, & Solanki, 2016). According to proponents of educational technology, the problem can be solved with the right tools (Odedra, Rabadiya, & Vidani, 2018).

Benefits of Ed-Tech for Teachers

The benefits of Ed-Tech extend beyond students. Innovation in schooling is being seen by educators as a method for coming up with compelling showing techniques and diminishing class time (Singh & Vidani, 2016)

The following are four different ways that Ed-Tech is helping teachers in getting back to what they excel at: educating (Singh & Vidani, 2016)

Automated Grading

The utilization of computer-based intelligence-controlled instructive innovation makes reviewing a breeze. These applications use AI to look at and rate reactions as per the necessities of the undertaking (Vidani & Plaha, 2016). When used for more objective assignments like true/false or fill-in-the-blank tests, these technologies can save teachers a significant amount of time compared to manual grading (Solanki & Vidani, 2016). With more time off, educators can spend less time preparing lessons and more time working one-on-one with students of varying ability levels (Vidani, 2016).

Classroom Management Tools

Can we just be real for a minute: getting an enormous gathering of children to do anything might challenge. All aspects of classroom life, from teacher-student interactions to student conduct, stand to benefit from the increased use of technological tools (Vidani, Chack, & Rathod, 2017). In addition to apps that help deliver reminders about projects or homework assignments, there are likewise advancements that permit understudies to self-screen study hall clamor levels (Biharani & Vidani, 2018). When management tools are used in the classroom, students learn in a setting that is less chaotic and more conducive to teamwork (Odedra, Rabadiya, & Vidani, 2018).

Paperless Classrooms

Thanks to advancements in educational technology, schools no longer have to worry about allotting funds for printers or waste paper or spending hours at the copy machine (Odedra, Rabadiya, & Vidani, 2018). Moving to a paperless system makes it easier to grade work, reduces the time spent searching for and organizing students' hundreds of homework files, and promotes greener teaching methods (Sachaniya, Vora, & Vidani, 2019).

Eliminating Guesswork

Teachers spend a lot of time trying to assess their pupils' strengths and opportunities for improvement (Vidani, 2019). The use of educational technology has the potential to change everything (Saxena & Vidani, 2023). Today, educators may take advantage of a plethora of resources, including data platforms, apps, and tools, that continuously assess their students' abilities and tailor instruction accordingly (Vidani, Jacob, & Patel, 2019).

The India Ed-Tech Industry is Taking India to the World

The Ed-Tech business in India has detonated over the most recent quite a long while, making it the world's focal point (Vidani J. N., 2016). The legislative area fills in as a facilitator while the confidential area expects a crucial job (Vidani & Plaha, 2017). The pandemic brought about a flood in Ed-Tech support for India's schooling area (Pathak & Vidani, 2016). There are without a doubt a few advantages of Ed-Tech over conventional training that should be considered. Now is the ideal time to characterize what our schooling area's new "ordinary"

will involve (Vidani & Singh, 2017).

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Ed-Tech empowers understudies who couldn't stick to the unbending cutoff times of the customary educational system to approach great training (Vidani, Meghrajani, & Siddarth, 2023). This is critical in low-pay families where kids often help their folks with work or housework during the day, when schools are typically in meetings (Odedra, Rabadiya, & Vidani, 2018). By filling in educator accessibility deficiencies, it likewise resolves the issue of students from such homes being not able to fund great regular training (Rathod, Meghrajani, & Vidani, 2022).

At last, Ed-Tech modules beat customary reading material when seen as an expansion to ordinary schooling as opposed to a total substitution (Vidani J. N., 2022). Further developed asset routes, sight and sound pictures, and intelligent elements accommodate a really fascinating instructive experience (Vidani & Das, 2021).

This is not to argue that Ed-Tech programmes are without difficulties and flaws of their own. The lack of proper infrastructure, poor accessibility, and the digital divide continues to impede the expansion of Ed-Tech (Vidani J. N., 2022). An Ed-Tech alliance is attempting to eradicate unfair business practices and misleading advertising that have lately come to light through self-regulation (Saxena & Vidani, 2023).

Globalizing: More than 4,450 Ed-Tech organizations in India are helping in excess of 300 million understudies in schools (Saxena & Vidani, 2023). Of these, 40 million are advanced education understudies whose reviews were slowed down by Coronavirus (Saxena & Vidani, 2023). The training quality hole between the rich and the poor in India could ultimately be shut by the country's Ed-Tech area, expanding the possibilities of accomplishment for Indians from every single financial foundation (Vidani, 2015). India's Ed-Tech blast is likewise a consequence of elements like the commonness of enthusiastic business people who foster state of the art items and strategies while approaching a huge pool of qualified instructors (Vidani & Solanki, 2015). These business people embrace a multicultural way to deal with address the issues of a country with a different populace (Vidani, 2015). Understudies from different nations are enlisting with Indian Ed-Tech organizations since they are reasonable as well as on the grounds that they give first rate happy (Solanki & Vidani, 2016).

Numerous Indian Ed-Tech organizations are bit by bit extending their overall impression by joining forces with abroad colleges or obtaining unfamiliar organizations (Bhatt, Patel, & Vidani, 2017). These organizations are extending on the grounds that they think their administrations are of excellent, and on the

grounds that worldwide agreements give them more noteworthy perceivability and admittance to subsidizing in created markets like the US. The new Public Schooling Strategy, 2020, which advances learning at worldwide colleges to assist with creating India as a center for worldwide instruction, has given these connections a lift (Niyati & Vidani, 2016). These joint efforts ought to give understudies admittance to between disciplinary projects and a first rate learning climate (Pradhan, Tshogay, & Vidani, 2016).

Our advanced gap is being shut by Indian Ed-Tech organizations working with the public area to give underserved bunches cross-country admittance to training. State legislatures have likewise answered the pandemic's test by making a learning biological system beyond the regular homeroom setting. A perfect representation is the Public Authority School Change Program, a piece of the Odisha government's 5T exertion (Straightforwardness, Collaboration, Innovation, and Practicality Prompting Change). To assist with shutting the computerized partition, it would likewise be useful for the state government to make tablet circulation rules in a joint effort with Ed-Tech firms (Modi, Harkani, Radadiya, & Vidani, 2016).

Contentment has always been to our advantage. We have witnessed the emergence of a whole sector in the last 10 years that uses technology to provide excellent content and novel solutions. State governments are responsible for utilizing these resources to their fullest potential for the good of the people (Sukhanandi, Tank, & Vidani, 2018).

In our 75th year of independence, India is justifiably claiming its place in the sun, and the Ed-Tech industry is a bright example of a sector that is exporting Indian pedagogy to the rest of the world (Singh, Vidani, & Nagoria, 2016). In the past, it generated news when an Indian-born executive rose to important leadership positions within Fortune 500 companies. Indian Ed-Tech businesses are now affecting both Indians and foreigners on a large scale by using Indian and other methodologies and tools (Mala, Vidani, & Solanki, 2016).

What is the Future of Ed-Tech in India?

The new cutbacks in the area are the consequence of a shift in course and realignment of the plan of action, expenses, and speculations, as per industry specialists. Ed-Tech isn't a prevailing fashion yet a reality that has encountered exceptional development throughout the course of recent years, is digging in for the long haul, and has a brilliant future (Dhere, Vidani, & Solanki, 2016).

The Ed-Tech sector in India, which was estimated to be worth \$750 million in 2020 and grow to \$4 billion by 2025, seems to be in trouble (Singh & Vidani, 2016). Due to the scale of the predicted market, India has excelled in the Ed-Tech sector. Following the pandemic, there was an abrupt development and rapid rise that benefited Indian Ed-Tech businesses (Vidani J. N., 2022). The Ed-Tech behemoth Byju's is reportedly planning to fire over 12,000 employees in 2019. This comes after the business earlier this month announced it would slash costs by terminating around 2,500 employees across departments (Vidani & Plaha, 2016). Byju's declared goals to lose around 5% of its 50,000 workers across divisions including item, happy, media, and innovation in stages over the course

of the following a half year, in what is reasonable perhaps of the biggest cutback by a significant startup (Solanki & Vidani, 2016).

Almost 45% of the 15,000+ cutbacks that the Indian startup biological system has seen for this present year might be credited to the Ed-Tech business. According to a report by Inc42, The Byju's made the most layoffs in the Ed-Tech sector, terminating roughly 4,000 workers across its companies (Solanki & Vidani, 2016).

In Kumar's opinion, businesses overdid their flamboyance in an effort to acquire companies, invest in goods, and attract customers and talent (Vidani, 2016).

"Due to the industry's explosive growth, it attracted investors, and hiring was done to prepare for future growth and to preserve competitive edge (Vidani, Chack, & Rathod, 2017). According to him, the pandemic hastened the acceptance of digitalization (Biharani & Vidani, 2018). Everything resumed normal operations after the lockdown was finished. The students desired to return to high school and college (Vidani, 2018). Ed-Tech is crucial to bridging the gap between the availability of qualified teachers and high-quality education in the most isolated areas of the nation (Sachaniya, Vora, & Vidani, 2019). Ed-Tech is a good option for students in K-12, higher education, or working learners (Odedra, Rabadiya, & Vidani, 2018).

The Ed-Tech alternative, according to Kumar, might be supplemental but not the main platform for learning (Vidani J. N., 2022). Virtual learning cannot totally replace actual campuses, student-teacher interactions, and student-student interactions (Vidani, Jacob, & Patel, 2019).

Even the most prominent colleges and universities were obliged to use a digital platform due to the Covid-induced global lockdown, which levelled the playing field for Ed-Tech firms that tapped into the digital domain to provide education and initially saw significant development for Ed-Tech companies (Vidani, Jacob, & Patel, 2019).

Why Has There Been a Sudden Decline in Ed-Tech Funding?

Up to four Ed-Tech companies, including Lido Learning, Crejo.Fun, Udayy, and SuperLearn, reportedly ceased operations as a result of the financial crisis, according to the Inc 42 story (Vidani & Pathak, 2016). According to Kumar, the expected sector growth has been lowered lower and the returns aren't in the anticipated range (Pathak & Vidani, 2016).

The majority of Ed-Tech businesses are losing money, which makes it necessary for them to review their business models in order to remain viable (Vidani J. N., 2022). The sector should once again be appealing for investment, albeit probably not at the same level, as financial discipline is starting to take hold (Pathak & Vidani, 2016). He went on to say that since the time is ideal for consolidation, mergers might be forthcoming (Vidani & Plaha, 2017).

According to Chandra, the finance crunch is merely temporary and the industry will rebound in the upcoming months (Vidani J. N., 2020). The demand for skilled developers and data scientists is at an all-time high, which has led to an increase of users on upskilling platforms (Vidani J. N., 2022). Another reason

boosting demand is the availability of web development and data science courses for working professionals at any time that suits them without interfering with their work (Vidani & Dholakia, 2020).

What Lies Ahead for Ed-Tech in India?

Education technology, according to industry analysts, has had amazing growth over the past two years and is not a fad (Vidani, Meghrajani, & Siddarth, 2023). This is the reason why it would continue on its current track and have a bright future (Rathod, Meghrajani, & Vidani, 2022). He continued by saying that the introduction of the digital university and the establishment of online campuses by foreign universities strengthen the case for Ed-Tech (Rathod, Meghrajani, & Vidani, 2022).

"Society all in all has benefited. Ed-Tech has further developed instruction by making it more individualized, reasonable, impartial (shutting the financial hole between the well-off and low-pay gatherings), and open. The advanced separation should be shut, and availability should be expanded (Vidani & Das, 2021).

According to Saurabh Deep Singla, CHRO at upGrad, the leading higher education technology firm in Asia, Ed-Tech is still in its infancy and has a lot of potential to produce innovations and results that will improve the lives of millions of people (Vidani J. N., 2022).

"We are seeing a more grounded take-up of on the web and Ed-Tech things among purchasers with India's rising web based entrance, but genuinely talking, it's at a starting stage (Vidani J. N., 2022). Energetic business visionaries have fostered their items and administrations to empower a continuous progression of training while likewise speeding up India's education chart across non-metros and provincial districts, because of the absence of customary learning open doors – or, I ought to say, a breakdown – as of late, he proceeded (Saxena & Vidani, 2023).

As per the PwC India study named "Startup Arrangements Tracker - Q3 CY22," financing in the Ed-Tech area has showed a positive pattern when contrasted with the earlier quarter (in esteem terms).

UpGrad, which raised \$225 million in Q3 CY22, and Sunstone, which raised \$35 million, each contributed 81% of the funding activity. According to Chandra, the startup world's Ed-Tech environment is thriving (Vidani, 2015).

"It's a lot more thrilling than it ever was. In the past two to three years, the business has witnessed a sharp rise in the number of startups, with thousands of new companies joining the market, according to him (Vidani & Solanki, 2015). As per a new Technavio examination on the internet based schooling market, India's market is supposed to create at a CAGR of 21% somewhere in the range of 2020 and 24 to arrive at a market size of US\$ 14.33 billion, exhibiting that the fate of this industry is exceptionally brilliant. A huge undiscovered market will assist with guaranteeing a brilliant future for Ed-Tech organizations in India as Web utilization is rising and public consciousness of Ed-Tech and computerized advancements is ascending across remote and rustic regions (Niyati & Vidani, 2016).

The fundamental issues facing the education sector arise from a variety of contexts, from technological and infrastructure issues to behavioural ones. In order to create a sufficient educational infrastructure and delivery system for inclusive learning, Ed-Tech businesses must collaborate with both public and private educational institutions, he continued (Niyati & Vidani, 2016).

The research work is divided in Three Phases

- Diagnosis Phase
- Design & Analysis Phase
- Implementation Phase

The first step of a is the diagnosis phase, during which the researcher looks for chances for improving the firm or organization in question as well as the difficulties it currently faces. Every study project begins with an issue (Modi, Harkani, Radadiya, & Vidani, 2016). A problem is a positive assumption that a researcher makes in order to carry out a research project or solve a problem that would, in turn, allow the specific organization or company to solve the problem and advance toward company upgradation (Modi, Harkani, Radadiya, & Vidani, 2016).

The COVID-19 outbreak brought the entire world to a standstill, and the education sector was among the worst affected globally. Nearly everyone's trust was also rocked by this pandemic (Mala, Vidani, & Solanki, 2016). As a result, CleverMinds CJ has a great deal of potential to help people regain their faith and confidence (Singh & Vidani, 2016).

As part of MAP, the first task we have to complete is to pinpoint opportunities and difficulties for the corporation we've chosen, CleverMinds CJ. From there, we'll strive to address issues pertaining to business operations (Solanki & Vidani, 2016).

Disadvantages of Not Having Hybrid Classes:

- Using time effectively turns into an issue for understudies who carry on with a separation from grounds.
- No recording or other type of information is dependably accessible for understudies who missed the class or later references. Students may not have the opportunity to learn about emerging technology.
- A lack of cutting-edge technologies.
- Expensive learning method.
- Limited learning time.
- Reliance on educators.

Problem Identification

CleverMinds. CJ is an offline service that offers corporate training for businesses to improve staff morale and English proficiency (Vidani, Chack, & Rathod, 2017). They are unable to see the big picture because of their limited reach. They are also unable to make enough money due to their restricted reach, and profit maximization is a growing issue as can be shown here (Vidani, 2018). They were conducting offline sessions and attending workshops, which, sadly,

did not reach a large audience and ultimately worked against them (Biharani & Vidani, 2018).

1. Offline to Online Presence:

There was a major problem of providing lectures in offline mode due to the limitations of connectivity with a large number of students (Odedra, Rabadiya, & Vidani, 2018). Students must leave the class or learn the material on their own if they are unable to attend any classes. Online lessons are a better option than offline programs if someone is ill or has another obstacle preventing them from attending class (Vidani, 2018).

2. Target audience from group to individuals:

There was a problem in providing lectures on one to one basis due to the high-cost burden on individuals. The company is also facing a problem in finding students in group and that leads to the decline in the sale of the courses of the company (Odedra, Rabadiya, & Vidani, 2018). Sometimes there is also a problem of difference in level of understanding of students in groups, if one student cannot able to understand the topic then, all group members must repeatedly listen the concept. This leads to the wastage of time of all other group members (Odedra, Rabadiya, & Vidani, 2018).

3. Providing independent courses being delivered as a bundle:

The company is facing problem in providing courses independently instead of providing as a bundle. The company has the combined courses of all the topics and this lead to the problem for both, company and students. The company has to provide the courses in bundle and the students has to face the problem in learning the entire courses in bundle (Odedra, Rabadiya, & Vidani, 2018). This all leads to the decline in the morale of the students by just viewing the entire course only and this ultimately become the threat in the sale of the courses (Sachaniya, Vora, & Vidani, 2019)

Opportunities

If CleverMinds, a corporate training academy, expands its market online and starts offering its sessions as courses, it will have many opportunities and be more profitable. Through social media marketing, they can also advertise their courses and workshops all over the world (Odedra, Rabadiya, & Vidani, 2018). As they gain knowledge through COVID-19, they can begin taking online courses and offering online training, which will provide time and resource savings. They can collaborate with prestigious universities and outstanding individuals throughout the world to deliver guest lectures online (Vidani, 2019).

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- To identify the Problems faced by the company
- To identify the opportunities for the company
- To provide solutions to the company
- To showcase the solutions
- To implement the strategy to turn opportunities into action
- Analyzing the results of the implemented strategy

- Measuring the results

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Allen, et. al. (2002): More people than any other time in recent memory are attracted to new innovation and online schooling. Web based learning can be engaging as a technique to do our examinations from the comfort of our homes, whether we are working experts with different cutoff times or understudies with a few tasks due. Utilizing a web-based help like Google Homeroom to take language courses from a teacher can bring about more affordable one-on-one guidance. According to Hackman and Walker, who were quoted in Mike Allen (2002), technology can affect how students learn. remarked that because of various benefits a virtual or remote classroom offers, some people would favour the distance learning alternative. At the point when the innovation worked successfully and didn't block channel moves, understudies participating in intuitive web-based study halls communicated their bliss with the experience. The use of innovation by understudies might be opposed for various reasons. Understudies might feel that the intervened experience can't absolutely supplant the in that frame of mind since innovation looks bound to breakdown, they may not be accustomed to utilizing machines, and these variables may be generally present (Vidani J. N., 2022).

Biswas & Dey (2021): He did a concentrate on the benefits and disservices of online versus customary tutoring in India. Since every choice enjoys particular benefits and burdens contrasted with the other, it is difficult to pick which is the predominant choice. It is difficult to supplant the disconnected, eye to eye study halls utilized in conventional schooling systems. Web based learning is valuable for specific courses and can increase the instructive cycle to make it really captivating and participatory. Whenever life has gotten back to business as usual after the Coronavirus time, we ought to continue customary study hall guidance (Vidani J. N., 2018).

Singh et. al. (2021): Here directed a concentrate on the viability of on the web and disconnected learning in advanced education in India, Indonesia, and Malaysia with 100 respondents. The review's discoveries showed that customary homeroom guidance is more fruitful than web guidance (Vidani & Dholakia, 2020).

Darius, Gundabattini & Soloman (2021): She conducted a poll of 450 students on the usefulness of online teaching and learning techniques for college and university students. When using techniques like animations, PPTs, and video lectures, it has been discovered that online learning is beneficial (Vidani, Meghrajani, & Siddarth, 2023) .

Qazi, et. al. (2022): In order to compare conventional and online schooling at entailing COVID-19 epidemic, he conducted a cross-sectional study with 320 students. The study concluded that, in light of the pandemic, it is critical for governments and other global policymakers to address citizens' access to and usage of online learning resources (Rathod, Meghrajani, & Vidani, 2022).

Narsingoju (2018): The vast majority of respondents to the study, or 70.4%, said they would advise their friends to use e-learning techniques. Based on their overall effectiveness, online learning obtained a rating of 4/5, while offline

learning received a grade of 3/5 (Vidani & Das, 2021).

Sullivan (2011): Here the case assert that the efficacy of teaching and student learning are significantly influenced by the teachers' oral fluency in the target language. At least the teachers use directive language in the classroom to direct student behaviour and explain tasks (Saxena & Vidani, 2023).

Bluic & Wright, (2017): Here the case contend that blended learning research should concentrate on the nature of how to combine offline and online forms of learning and take into account the calibre of students' learning experiences. With these considerations in mind, the goal of this study is to establish whether or not face-to-face classroom instruction is superior to online classroom instruction (e-learning) (Vidani, 2015).

Mullen & Runnels (2006): Here the case declare that internet based courses are those that are altogether conveyed on the web. The Web and correspondence advances are utilized in electronic training, going from involving the Web as an exploration device to taking web-based courses. The Web is at times used to upgrade guidance, for example, when a site is utilized to refresh understudies signed up for up close and personal classes. Any course that is educated to understudies who are not in a similar homeroom is likewise alluded to as online schooling. These may be appropriated through Google Homeroom, online courses, and WhatsApp. Any discovering that is electronically intervened or worked with by exchanges programming can be alluded to as e-learning, says the case (Vidani, 2016).

Althaus (1997): This study investigates whether adding computer-mediated discussion (CMD) to in-person discussions in large lecture courses improves undergraduate students' academic achievement. It also looks at the traits of students who volunteer to participate in CMD groups even when doing so is voluntary and only earns a little bit of credit (Pradhan, Tshogay, & Vidani, 2016). A quasi-experimental study involving 142 undergraduates found that a combination of face-to-face and computer-mediated interaction creates a learning environment that is superior to that of the traditional classroom, according to student evaluations and academic performance statistics (Pradhan, Tshogay, & Vidani, 2016). Active participants in CMD groups not only claimed to have learned more than they otherwise would have, but they also tended to receive better grades than those who solely engaged in face-to-face conversation (Pradhan, Tshogay, & Vidani, 2016).

Interpretation

- According to the data, web based learning among understudies in advanced education is dull and tedious in light of the fact that understudies find it challenging to change in accordance with the numerous procedures of web based discovering that are accessible.
- When it comes to education, the offline technique of learning is considered to be the most effective choice owing to the fact that it is more straightforward and fundamental.
- Learning on the internet would be more efficient during the pandemic as well as in the future. The vast majority of students are of the opinion that

using online learning technologies will confer a great deal of advantages upon them, allowing them to learn more and improve their academic performance, given that manual labour and traditional classroom settings will likely become obsolete in the not too distant future.

- Previous research has demonstrated that the learning process is enhanced when offline or traditional education is supplemented with online learning platforms. This methodology is referred to as blended learning.
- However, students who live in remote locations from their college or institution may find that online learning is the most beneficial mode of instruction for them. The discoveries demonstrate that the greatest number of understudies accept that internet learning is the sole teaching method that saves them time while examining during the hour of Pandemic. This end depends on the outcomes, which show that the discoveries uncover the outcomes.
- Thusly, we can say that web based learning is the most effective way for the two educators and understudies to guarantee that there will be coherence in schooling from now on. Nonetheless, this method of teaching method online likewise has its entanglements, for example, challenges in educating, specialized issues, confined capacities to focus, and an absence of mindfulness among understudies.

Alternative Courses of Action

1. The First alternative that has been proposed to the CleverMinds.CJ is for it to switch from offline mode to Hybrid form in order to increase its reach. Research shows that companies can benefit from offering online courses. Your staff will be more prepared for the work ahead. When they improve in efficiency, you can deduct business costs more rapidly.

With the convenience of online learning, people are better able to expand their horizons and use what they've learned in their daily lives. Improving one's memory for extended periods of time is another benefit. The data we collect from students is crucial to developing better teaching methods and increasing retention rates. Evidence has demonstrated that e-learning platforms are more efficient at data collection and analytics processing than any other approach previously used (Modi, Harkani, Radadiya, & Vidani, 2016).

Colleges and universities can now collect and analyze data on student attrition rates, giving them a better idea of where they can improve their curriculum. Once the adjustments have been made, they can rerun the analyses to determine if the results have improved. Incredibly useful information can be gleaned from student records, but only in the future will its full usefulness be realized (Vidani, 2016).

The second suggestion is basically that, People should choose package courses based on their needs. No solution will satisfy everyone's desires. Online learning offers multiple learning styles to help students fit into their programs. Students are driven to pursue higher education without having to pass such unpleasant courses (Sukhanandi, Tank, & Vidani, 2018).

Online learning allows for student customization. It lets students set their own speed and route. E-learning saves money (Vidani J. N., 2022). Educational

institutions saved money on student and staff transportation and lodging, lowering prices. No expensive textbooks increase student debt. The process is eco-friendly because text material printing is not needed (Dhere, Vidani, & Solanki, 2016).

The last proposition we have made is to adjust the technique for showing utilizing accounts. In an ordinary homeroom, teachers stick to their blunder inclined methods of guidance. E-learning wipes out these worries by offering normalized and steady instructing (Vidani J. N., 2022). Web based learning empowers educators to convey normal examples with more inclusion, guaranteeing that all understudies get a similar measure of information (Vidani, Chack, & Rathod, 2017).

There is a deficiency of talented teachers in numerous establishments all over the planet. With e-learning, a couple of profoundly taught and experienced teachers might train hundreds, on the off chance that not huge number of understudies (Odedra, Rabadiya, & Vidani, 2018) .

A unique advantage of e-learning is that you can access the study materials as many times as necessary. Forget about hunching over your desk in an attempt to catch every lecturer's word while scribbling notes in handwriting that not even Enigma could read (Odedra, Rabadiya, & Vidani, 2018).

Online courses provide you with the flexibility to successfully study for your exams without having to rush to campus.

METHODS

This particular report was compiled via secondary data analysis, which is utilizing the data that someone else has collected for their own reasons. Using secondary data analysis, researchers seek to answer a new research topic or investigate an alternative perspective on the original subject of a previous study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Solution Implementation

Figure 1. Udeemy Platform

On the Udemy platform, the remedy to enhance exposure was delivered utilizing hybrid mode, and it was successful. Udemy, Inc. is a firm that specializes in educational technologies and offers a digital platform for the purpose of providing education and training to students. We have created a number of courses that are available for purchase on the Udemy website thanks to the establishment of a specific identifier for our use of the platform. This approach makes it feasible to provide online instruction over a broad spectrum of topics, which paves the way for a large number of additional students to get access to higher education.

	An Extensive Training Programme for IELTS (Writing)	\$0.00 Earned this month	0 Enrollments this month	0.00 Course rating
	An Extensive Training Programme for the IELTS (Reading)	\$0.00 Earned this month	0 Enrollments this month	0.00 Course rating
	An Extensive Training Programme for the IELTS (Writing)	\$0.00 Earned this month	0 Enrollments this month	0.00 Course rating
	An Extensive Training Programme for the IELTS (Reading)	\$0.00 Earned this month	0 Enrollments this month	0.00 Course rating

Figure 2. Udemy Platform 2

To assist people in learning English in all four skills –reading, writing, speaking, and listening—we have produced audio and video lessons in both languages. These lessons can be accessed through our website (Hindi and English). We have also taken steps to differentiate each course from the others so that students will have a better opportunity to select the classes that most interest them. In addition to this, it will be of assistance to them because it will enable them to choose the appropriate course for them at a price that is within their financial means.

Figure 3. Udemy Platform 3

In addition to this, we have proposed that ma'am create recordings, both audio, and video, to utilize in her classes. In this approach, the student or subscriber will not only have access to a course of study but also to a collection of tools with which to put what they've learned into practice. Both the teacher and the student have the ability to customize their experience to some extent thanks to this feature. In addition to that, we have provided students with access to sample tests as well as other resources that have been tailored to the particular requirements of their courses as well as the kind of assessments that they will be taking.

CONCLUSION

I. Better Student Engagement:

Some understudy were brought up in when cell phones, tablets, and other mechanical gadgets were normal; thus, they are most likely acquainted with involving innovation for work and school. Innovation coordination into the homeroom empowers teachers to cooperate with understudies and disperse course material in a setting where understudies feel great and secure.

II. Variability for Learners:

Understudies have more command over their learning and can associate with course material in the ways that turn out best for them on the grounds that to the sheer scope of computerized data tracked down in the standard web-based course part - text, video, testing, and interactives.

A few understudies will decide to peruse texts instead of watch motion pictures. some do the inverse. Others could start by self-assessing the course material. In the event that a system supports learning, it is legitimate. The utilization of advanced media builds understudies' command over their schooling.

III. Flexibility for Teachers:

Educators' span is extended by instructive innovation beyond class time and available time. Computerized reviewing gives educators additional opportunity to draw in with understudies in significant and individual ways. With the guide of innovation, teachers today have more instructive devices available to them to draw in and challenge more understudies.

It is less difficult for educators to help students in learning the substance in light of the range of choices available to them. Each understudy's way of learning relies upon their capacity to learn and concentrate on according to their very own preferences.

IV. Personalization and Connection:

With crossover courses, understudies can associate with their companions beyond class time in manners that permit all understudies to partake to help and show each other. This is invaluable for the understudies since it gives them the opportunity to coordinate their own learning and follow their advantage. Whenever allowed the opportunity to work with their companions, half and half learning might support working on how they might interpret the subject.

V. Better use of resources:

Certain individuals like web based learning over face to face guidance. Various methodologies and data sources are converged in mixture learning. Understudies are hence bound to know about what suits them by and by. Individuals can focus on their own learning styles while saving time and exertion. Subsequently, individuals can procure valuable abilities and put them to rapidly use in reality more.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations so further research is still needed on the topic of a review of Ed-Tech sector in India.

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